

THE CONCEPT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING GROUPS AND ORGANIZING
PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING FOR STUDENT GROUPS

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Abstract. *In this study, we presented our ideas and proposals on the use of psychological training based on new innovative psychological approaches in order to improve the quality of education based on multi-vector approaches currently used in modern education. In modern education, there are opportunities to use psychological methods to improve students' cooperation skills based on pedagogical and psychological approaches. Taking advantage of these opportunities, we developed modern educational mechanisms using psychological training as a modern educational method. Organizing trainings through the organization of psychological training groups helps groups of students to learn together, collectively.*

Keywords: *Psychological training, psychologist-trainers, psychological approaches, collaborative learning, psychological potential, education, pedagogical research.*

КОНЦЕПЦИЯ ГРУПП ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ И ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ
ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ СТУДЕНЧЕСКИХ ГРУПП

Аннотация. *В данном исследовании мы представили наши идеи и предложения по использованию психологического тренинга на основе новых инновационных психологических подходов в целях повышения качества образования на основе многовекторных подходов, используемых в настоящее время в современном образовании. В современном образовании существуют возможности использования психологических методов для совершенствования навыков сотрудничества учащихся на основе педагогических и психологических подходов.*

Используя эти возможности, мы разработали современные образовательные механизмы, используя психологический тренинг как современный метод обучения. Организация учебных занятий путем организации групп психологов помогает группам студентов учиться вместе, коллективно.

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Ключевые слова: Психологическая подготовка, психологи-тренеры, психологические подходы, совместное обучение, психологический потенциал, образование, педагогические исследования.

PSIXOLOGIK TRENING GURUHLARI TUSHUNCHASI VA TALABALAR GURUHLARIGA PSIXOLOGIK TRENINGLAR TASHKILLASHTIRISH

Аннотация: Ushbu tadqiqotda biz hozirgi vaqtda zamonaviy ta'limda qo'llanilayotgan ko'p vektorli yondashuvlar asosida ta'lim sifatini oshirish maqsadida yangi innovatsion psixologik yondashuvlar asosida psixologik treningdan foydalanish bo'yicha o'z fikr va takliflarimizni taqdim etdik. Zamonaviy ta'limda pedagogik va psixologik yondashuvlar asosida o'quvchilarning hamkorlik ko'nikmalarini oshirish uchun psixologik usullardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari mavjud. Bu imkoniyatlardan unumli foydalanib, psixologik treningdan zamonaviy ta'lim usuli sifatida foydalangan holda zamonaviy ta'lim mexanizmlarini ishlab chiqdik. Psixologik trening guruhlarini tashkil qilish orqali treninglarni tashkillashtirish talabalar guruhlarini birgalikda, jamoaviy holda ta'lim olishga yordam beradi.

Калит so'zlar: Psixologik trening, psixolog-trenerlar, psixologik yondashuvlar, hamkorlikda ta'lim, psixologik salohiyat, ta'lim, pedagogik tadqiqotlar.

INTRODUCTION

The development of collaborative skills among students is important in modern education, as teamwork and problem-solving in groups are important in both academic and professional settings. This article examines pedagogical mechanisms designed to enhance collaborative skills through the implementation of a multi-vector approach. The multi-vector method emphasizes a variety of teaching strategies that allow students to participate in dynamic, interactive learning processes. By combining elements such as collaborative learning, peer interaction, and interdisciplinary tasks, this approach develops students' ability to collaborate effectively. Our research also examines the role of teachers in facilitating these processes and promoting an environment in which communication, creativity, and critical thinking flourish. The practical use of a multi-vector approach has a positive effect on students' collaborative skills, making them effective in solving real problems in their future careers. This study is devoted to improving students' collaborative skills through psychological training and pedagogical methods. We believe that it is appropriate to use collaborative teaching methods in creating a new system based on multi-vector approaches in education.

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We further increase the effectiveness of education by forming students' worldviews, improving their collaborative skills, and consolidating their knowledge through psychological training. Through this study, we examined the most effective method of group and collective learning. We put forward the idea that this increases students' ability to remember the acquired knowledge, helps them to think freely, reason, and make decisions. During this study, we conducted interviews with students through psychological training and listened to students' opinions.

Psychological research provides a brief theoretical overview of research on active and collaborative learning in education. Definitions of these learning forms are given. The main features of active and collaborative learning forms are listed. Types of learning activities used in collaborative learning are listed: discussion, peer learning, problem solving, joint writing, games. Possible reasons for the effectiveness of collaborative learning are indicated: socio-psychological factors and the ability to provide a high level of cognitive participation. Based on these studies, information is provided on the practical application of research based on modern pedagogical methods and the organization of psychological trainings to improve students' collaborative skills.

Despite the variety of psychological exercises used in psychological training sessions, the variety of teaching techniques of teachers and the variety of pedagogical methods used by psychologists in organizing psychological training sessions, it is possible to single out methodological problems in several main psychological training methods. Most of them, in the process of collaborative learning (i.e., students working in groups in the process of collaborative learning), traditionally include group discussions and situational role-playing. In addition, researchers - theorists and practicing psychologists who solve the methodological problems of psychological training - propose to include in the main training methods such as methods based on psychophysiological self-management through the training of interpersonal sensitivity, including training aimed at increasing the sensitivity of students to perception in collaborative learning in a collective manner. Also, the use of meditative methods and stimulating (for teaching self-hypnosis) methods in psychological training sessions is recommended to pedagogical psychologists. The organization of psychological trainings is mainly based on the idea that group discussion is a joint (collaborative) discussion of any controversial issue, which allows clarifying the opinions, positions and relationships of group members (possibly changing, reasoning, free thinking) in the process of direct communication. We put forward the idea that the use of psychological training that enhances collaborative skills in the education system helps to form the worldview of students. We believe that it is appropriate to use collaborative teaching methods in creating a new system based on multi-vector approaches in education.

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We put forward the idea that this increases the ability of students to remember the knowledge they have received, helps them think freely, reason, and make decisions. During this study, we conducted interviews with students through psychological training and listened to their opinions. Based on it, information is provided on the use of modern methods for improving students' collaborative skills through psychological training and pedagogical methods based on multiple vectors in higher education. Through the stages of creating modern educational institutions, we can achieve an effective educational program through the integration of innovative ideas of education, modern psychological training. By improving the collaborative skills of students, we will not be mistaken if we say that we create conditions for forming their worldview, educating them as a spiritually enlightened young generation, increasing their ability to express their opinions independently, improving their free decision-making skills, and educating them as complete people.

Group discussions in training can also be used to give participants the opportunity to look at the problem arising in psychological training from different perspectives (this will identify mutual positions that reduce resistance to mutual guidance and acceptance of new information from other members of the group), and as a way to overcome the psychological methodological problem of group reflection through individual analysis. As a result, this experience strengthens the unity of the group and at the same time helps participants to reveal their world. We believe that there are various reasons for classifying the forms of group discussion in the implementation of psychological training in collaborative education. In structured discussions, the main reasons for the emergence of methodological problems in psychological training are determined by the topic of discussion, and sometimes their order is clearly regulated. Unstructured discussions are characterized by the role of the facilitator in the passive psychological methodological problem-solving methodology, the topics of which are chosen at their discretion, the time of the discussion is not formally limited, the conditions of psychological training are explained, the rules of the team are explained. In addition, in psychological training, psychologists can consider thematic discussions, in which topics that are important for all participants in the training are discussed; biographical based on past experience; interactive methods, the structure and content of the relationship between group members, pedagogically and psychologically based sources are used. Discussion methods are used in the analysis of various situations, from the life or life of the participants of the training, in the analysis of complex situations in interpersonal relationships proposed by the psychologist, and in other cases.

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Game methods include situational role-playing, didactic, creative, organizational-activity, imitation, business games. The use of game methods in training, according to many researchers, is very effective. At the first stage of group (collaborative) work, games are useful for overcoming the mental depression and mental tension of the participants, as a condition for painless removal of psychological defenses. The game method based on psychological training very often becomes a means of self-diagnosis, based on diagnostics that allow, with caution, to easily identify communication difficulties and the presence of serious psychological problems.

CONCLUSION

Information on the use of pedagogical methods and psychological training as modern stages of collaborative education was presented. We will talk about the importance of using psychological training in improving students' collaborative skills based on modern educational programs. During our study, information was provided on the rules for organizing psychological training, based on the pedagogical skills and psychological potential of the teacher. Instructions were also given on the application of psychological training to a group of students, including expanding students' knowledge through psychological methods. If psychological training is organized according to these instructions, we will contribute to the development of students as a capable, harmonious generation, intelligent, well-educated young people, achieving high results in education.

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